

Mini-review

Management of pain during castration in male calves

Isabelle Veissier, Alice de Boyer des Roches

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CARE4DAIRY

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1. The issue

Male calves are castrated to suppress the production of male hormones, with a view to reduce aggression between animals, ensure the safety of caretakers, and eliminate the risk of unwanted pregnancies in the herd. In addition, steers (which are castrated bovine animals aged 1 year or older) can be mixed with heifers without the risk of unwanted mating in the herd. Depending on the country, most calves are castrated (to produce steers) or left intact (to produce beef bulls). There are several methods of castration, all of which are painful for the animal. Early life pain is likely to alter later pain sensitivity and behavioural reactivity (Adcock, 2021). Adequate pain management during castration is therefore critical to animal welfare in both the short and long term. This review summarises the knowledge on pain and pain management during calf castration.

2. Summary of the scientific knowledge¹

2.1. Methods for castration

2.1.1. Bloodless methods

Elastration (sometimes refer to as banding): A latex band or a rubber ring is placed about 0.5 cm above the testicles, blocking blood circulation and causing testicular necrosis. (see for instance <https://www.afac.ab.ca/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/AFAC-BANDING-CASTRATION-FACT-SHEET.pdf>). Elastration causes ischaemic necrosis of the testes and leads to testicular atrophy and scrotal sloughing. Small rubber rings (rubber ring castration) are used for calves less than 1-month old. For older calves, thick-walled latex bands are used with a grommet to secure the mechanically tightened tube at the appropriate tension.

Emasculator (Burdizzo clamp): A clamp is pressed onto the spermatic cords for ~10 s. It crushes the blood vessels, suppresses blood flow to the testicles and results in testicular necrosis. (see for instance <https://www.afac.ab.ca/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/page7.pdf>)

2.1.2. Surgical method

Surgery (sometimes refer to as knife castration): The scrotum is incised (e.g. with a Newberry knife) and the testicles are pulled out, then either 1- the blood vessels above each testicle are crushed as in the previous method, or 2- the spermatic cord is twisted until the testicles fall off, or 3- the spermatic cord is stretched until it ruptures.

¹ The scientific reviews prepared for CARE4DAIRY focused on the literature of the last 10 years, assuming that older articles have already been taken into account in current technical recommendations. Older articles may be cited if they provide complementary knowledge.

When the testicles are not removed, the tissue necrosis can take weeks. Healing is complete by 6-8 weeks (Becker et al., 2012). Healing is faster after surgical castration than after elastration (1 month vs. 2 months, Nogues et al., 2021).

2.1.3. Hormonal method

Immunisation: immunisation against gonadotropin-releasing factor results in reduced plasma testosterone concentrations and hence reduced physical activity in bulls. It has been proposed as a welfare-friendly alternative to castration because it does not cause pain or stress (Marti et al., 2015). However, to our knowledge this practice is not used in Europe².

2.2. Pain during castration

Bloodless and surgical methods of castration involve the cutting of tissues and therefore cause acute and chronic pain.

Signs of short-term pain (immediately after castration) include:

- animal struggling and mooing during castration
- increase in blood cortisol shortly after castration: after a peak during the 1st hour after castration, cortisol levels return to baseline within a few hours (Meléndez et al., 2018b; Nogues et al., 2021); a secondary increase in cortisol can be observed in older calves (5 months, Marquette et al., 2021)
- transient decrease in heart rate immediately after castration (6-month-old calves, Dockweiler et al., 2013)
- increase in substance P in blood (Dockweiler et al., 2013)
- increase in acute phase proteins in blood (Earley and Crowe, 2002)

Signs of long-term pain (for several days or weeks after castration) include:

- Foot stamping (Van der Saag et al., 2018),
- Altered gait: 'stiff gait' (walking slowly with stiff muscles, e.g. Van der Saag et al., 2018) or walking with more weight on the forelimbs (Kleinhenz et al., 2018)
- Increased sensitivity of the area around the wound (response to palpation or response to von Frey hairs, Norring et al., 2017)
- Reduced lying time (Meléndez et al., 2018a)
- Restlessness assessed by frequency of lying down and getting up (Robertson et al., 1994; Molony et al., 1995)
- Reduced number of steps (Daniel et al., 2020)
- Qualitative behaviour assessment: reduced activity and reduced engagement with the environment (Vindevoghel et al., 2018)
- Licking of the lesion (Becker et al., 2012)

² Some products are available (e.g. https://www.zoetis.co.nz/_locale-assets/doc/species-products/bopriva-veterinary-guide.pdf)

- Reduced appetite (lower food intake, longer latency to start eating when food is offered) (reviewed in Coetzee, 2013a)
- Reduced weight gain (Marti et al., 2015)

Long-term pain is associated with inflammation in the scrotal region. Inflammation can be observed from the aspect of the lesion (e.g. swelling, incomplete healing), scrotal temperature, Acute Phase Proteins in the blood, rectal temperature.

Surgical castration causes more short-term pain than elastration (Meléndez et al., 2017b; Gellatly et al., 2021) whereas elastration causes more chronic pain (more licking of the lesion, less time spent lying down, reduced daily weight gain) than surgical castration due to delayed but prolonged inflammation (Moya et al., 2014; Nogues et al., 2021).

There are few studies in the scientific literature from the last 10 years comparing Burdizzo castration with other methods. Burdizzo castration appears to be slightly less painful than surgical castration in the short term, with animals less likely to lick the lesion (Pieler et al., 2013). In fact, surgical castration involves an incision in the scrotum and pulling out the testicles, in addition to crushing the spermatic cord. Burdizzo castration may cause slightly more long-term pain due to prolonged inflammation and the resulting slower healing process.

Up to 2 months of age, calves appear to experience less pain during castration, or at least to be less stressed than at 3-6 months (lower cortisol response: Dockweiler et al., 2013; Meléndez et al., 2017b; Bergamasco et al., 2021). Six-month-old calves may experience pain so severe that it cannot be relieved by local anaesthesia and analgesia (Park et al., 2018). Inflammation is more pronounced immediately after castration in young calves (few days old) than in older calves (2.5 months of age), resulting in a greater local sensitivity but faster healing (Norrington et al., 2017).

Castration is more painful for calves than disbudding (Mosher et al., 2013). Castration combined with disbudding may be more painful than castration alone (Sutherland et al., 2013) although the cumulative effects of the two procedures are not always clear (Mosher et al., 2013).

2.3. Pain management during castration

2.3.1. Analgesia

Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (**NSAIDs**) can reduce the pain experienced by animals. A number of drugs have been tested: Ketoprofen (Moya et al., 2014), Flunixin Meglumine (Nordi et al., 2019), and Meloxicam.

Meloxicam appears to be the most effective NSAID. Meloxicam can be administered subcutaneously (0.5 mg/kg Body Weight (BW); Vindevoghel et al., 2018; Melendez et al., 2019) or orally (0.5 mg/kg BW in Van der Saag et al., 2018; 1 mg/kg BW in Melendez et al., 2019). Meloxicam is best given immediately before castration rather than several hours before (Meléndez et al., 2017a). However, analgesia with Meloxicam administered

immediately before castration is not sufficient to eliminate pain at the time of castration but reduces inflammation (haptoglobin) and pain after castration (cortisol 2 – 48 h after castration, more time lying down and less standing up) (Gellaly et al., 2021; Daniel et al., 2020; Meléndez et al., 2018a; Meléndez et al., 2018b).

2.3.2. Anaesthesia

Local anaesthesia (e.g. Lidocaine or Procaine³ injected in the scrotum or the spermatic cord (30 mL Licaine 2% in Nordi et al., 2019; 2 mg/kg BW Lidocaine in Vindevoghel et al., 2018; 10 mL Procaine 2% in Pieler et al., 2013) or regional anaesthesia (by epidural injection of e.g. 0.2 mg/kg Lidocaine in Coetzee, 2013b) relieves acute pain during castration. Lidocaine can be toxic and cause convulsions at high doses. Based on data obtained on sheep and goats, 10 mg /kg BW appear to be the maximum that can be administered (Venkatachalam et al., 2018).

Anaesthesia eliminates the cortisol peak and behavioural responses such as struggling during castration (Meléndez et al., 2018b). The anaesthetic drug must be administered immediately before castration. In fact, local anaesthesia is effective a few minutes after administration (2-5 min) and lasts up to 90 min; regional anaesthesia takes longer to become effective (~10 min after administration) and has a longer duration of action (115 min) (reviewed by Coetzee, 2013a). Injection into the epidural space is more technically demanding than a subcutaneous and spermatic cord injection. In our opinion, local anaesthesia is much easier and more practical to perform than epidural anaesthesia. Topical anaesthesia with a gel sprayed on the wound immediately after castration is also possible (gel containing lignocaine, bupicaine, an antiseptic (cetrimide), and adrenaline, Van der Saag et al., 2018) but covers only postoperative pain.

2.3.3. Anaesthesia combined with analgesia

NSAIDs and anaesthetics act at different times: anaesthesia relieves the pain at the time of the castration and NSAIDs relieve pain after castration (Meléndez et al., 2018b, see Figure 1). The combination of anaesthesia and analgesia provides pain relief from the time of castration for several hours or days.

2.3.4. Disinfection

Several factors influence the healing process: age, nutrition, health status, asepsis and protection of the wound (Harper et al., 2014). Surgical castration should be performed on a clean and possibly disinfected skin and asepsis should be maintained during the

³ Some products may not be authorised for farm animals in some countries. For instance, Lidocaine is not authorised in France whereas procaine is.

procedure. An antiseptic may be sprayed on the wound immediately after castration (Van der Saag et al., 2018).

Figure 1. Least square mean for salivary cortisol (nmol/L) of weaned Angus crossbreeds calves with (Melox+Lido) or without (Control) a lidocaine ring block and a single s.c. meloxicam injection (adapted from Meléndez et al., 2018b).

2.3.5. Healing agents

To date, the effects of applying a healing agent to the wound have not been proven (Marti et al., 2017).

2.3.6. Sedation

Xylazine (0.2 mg/kg BW) administered prior to castration reduces animal alertness, induces muscle relaxation and provides some systemic analgesia; it reduces the animal's responses during castration and eliminates the cortisol peak. However, a rebound in plasma cortisol is observed shortly after the effects of Xylazine wear off (reviewed by Coetzee, 2013a). Xylazine sedation alone does not appear to be effective in relieving pain castration pain.

3. Recommendations

If male calves are to be castrated, we recommend:

- Castration in the first two months of life
- Avoiding methods that cause prolonged pain. Short-term pain can be relieved by anaesthesia and analgesia at the time of castration. Prolonged pain is more difficult to alleviate because it requires repeated treatment. For this reason, we do not recommend band castration. Instead surgical castration by a veterinarian should be recommended, otherwise Burdizzo castration by the farmer⁴.
- Pain management including 1- sedation with Xylazine⁵ to reduce stress and induce muscle relaxation and short-term systemic analgesia, 2- local anaesthesia to eliminate short-term pain during the procedure, and 3- analgesia with an NSAID (e.g. Meloxicam) to reduce pain after castration. As in the case for disbudding in several countries, farmers should be trained then allowed to administer these products on their own calves under veterinary supervision.
- Paying attention to skin cleanliness and disinfection if surgical castration is used.⁶
- Observing calves closely for several days after castration to detect any signs of poor health due to local or general infection (e.g. infection at the site of the lesion, poor healing, fever, loss of appetite): a few days in the case of surgical castration, up to 10 days in the case of Burdizzo castration.

4. Literature search

Search equation in WOS: same as for the review "Recognition of pain signs in cows".

Topic: pain AND (cattle OR cow OR cows OR calf OR calves OR heifer?) AND (sign? OR indicator?)

Date: 01/01/2012 to 30/06/2022

27 articles dealing with castration were extracted, of which 4 were removed because they were abstracts to conferences and the results have now been published in journal articles.

7 articles added: Coetze 2013a, Harper et al 2014, Kleinhenz et al. 2018; Adcock et al 2021.; Robertson et al., 1994; Molony et al., 1995.

⁴ Concerning the use of the Burdizzo method, it is very important that the clamp lines above each testicle are not exactly opposite to each other as they would block blood circulation and carry a risk of gangrene.

⁵ Can be injected intravenously (0.03 à 0.1 mg/kg depending on the degree of the sedation expected) or in intramuscular (higher dosage).

⁶ In case of surgical castration performed by a veterinarian, antibiotics can be administered after castration, otherwise calves should be isolated in very clean pens. The skin must be kept clean for 2-3 days after castration.

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